

The International Criminal Court and Theories of Relationship with the United Nations, States and Non State Parties in Criminal Justice Issues*¹

ABSTRACT

Preliminary analysis of the relationship of the International Criminal Court (ICC) with most countries in carrying out its functions of investigation, arrests and possible prosecution, where the court has conducted investigations and carried out some actions suggests that the ICC must delicately balance its relationships with governments in countries in which it has opened an investigation. It has to maintain the state's cooperation in order to gain the access it needs to collect evidence and make arrests. In some cases, the ICC has been criticized for the choices it has made in terms of investigation and prosecution which most often threatens safety and security of the victims and other vulnerable citizens. The research aims at analysing the theories of relationship of the International Criminal Court with the United Nations, States and Non State Parties in Criminal Justice Issues. The objective of this research is to highlight the implications and difficulties in collecting evidence for indictment and arrest in a violent environment. The study adopts doctrinal designs using analytical approach with reliance made on Statutes, case law, law reviews and data in web-based sources which will be subjected to content analysis. The research found that the presence of the ICC personal alone creates tension in the mind of any indicted sitting president and if the situation is not carefully handled, the ICC personal is seen as a hostile visitor conniving with citizens to outrun the government. The citizens are always at the receiving end. Consequently, there is need for a balance in relationship to enable elicitation of evidence, possible arrest and prosecution of perpetrators of the international crime(s) in question.

Keywords: International Criminal Court, Theories of Relationship, United Nations, States and Non State Parties, Criminal Justice Issues

1. INTRODUCTION

The International Criminal Court (ICC) is established as an independent entity able to try individuals for crimes within its jurisdiction, without a mandate from the United Nations.² The Rome Statute established the ICC as a permanent international criminal court for the investigation and prosecution of individuals who commit acts that constitute international crimes as provided under the statute.³ The ICC is the first treaty-based permanent international criminal court. It is intended primarily to regulate and ensure accountability for international crimes, to prosecute and punish perpetrators of war crimes and crimes against humanity. The court is intended to act complementarily with states national courts but under the principle of complementarity, it is enabled to try individuals only when national courts are unwilling or unable genuinely do so. Consequently, State Parties to the Rome Statute preemptorily submitted themselves to the jurisdiction of the ICC for the crimes outlined in the Statute. Nonetheless, the ICC may

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² On 4 October 2004, the ICC and the United Nations signed an agreement governing their institutional relationship. See: Understanding the International Criminal Court by the Public Information and Documentation Section Registry, International Criminal Court The Hague.

³ Article 1 of the Rome Statute.

only exercise jurisdiction over Member States for crimes which occurred after the establishment of the ICC in 2002. The Court may not pursue offenses retroactively, unless authorised by the Member State of the individual in question.⁴ It is worthy of note that the Court prosecutes individuals, and not groups or states and no one is exempted from prosecution based on status or Office⁵. The principle of complementarity upholds that national courts take priority over the ICC, unless the domestic courts are unable or unwilling to conduct trials.⁶ Nonetheless, The United Nations Security Council may also exercise its power under Article 13(b) of the Rome Statute and refer a situation to the ICC Prosecutor for investigation and prosecution. The court is determined to put an end to impunity for the perpetrators of international crimes and thus to contribute to the prevention of such crimes. However, it has been observed that a narrow focus on criminal justice administration and its process by the ICC has the potential to destabilise peace negotiations, deepen security and safety threats and delay speedy administration of criminal justice as well. Part I of the study is on the introduction while part II discussed the relationship of the ICC with the United Nations, The ICC and Africa, ICC and the United States of America. Part III is a Critique of the ICC as a Neocolonial Venture. It further discussed the ICC and Peace Processes. Part IV is the Conclusion and Recommendations.

2. International Criminal Court and Theories of Relationship with the United Nations, States and Non State Parties in Criminal Justice Issues

(a) ICC and the United Nations

The ICC, though independent, has formed an institutional relationship with the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) which relationship was formalised in 2004.⁷ The UN Security Council, consisting of five permanent representatives of the five permanent member states with veto power⁸ and 10 non-permanent members elected by the General Assembly for a two-year term, may refer a case to the ICC invoking Chapter VII of the UN Charter.⁹ Additionally, the UNSC may defer an investigation or prosecution for a renewable period of twelve months. The relationship between the Security Council and the ICC in referring a situation to the court, and the application of complementarity regime is not very clear. While article 18 of the Rome Statute¹⁰ does not apply to Security Council referrals, article 19¹¹ does. It has been argued that the complementary regime does not as such apply to such referral.¹² The Security Council in a resolution referring a situation to the court may declare a situation admissible, for example by declaring a state unable or unwilling to investigate or prosecute. The question is whether the

⁴ The International Criminal Court: Origins, Jurisdiction and the 'African Bias' South African History Online © 2015 <http://www.sahistory.org.za/article/international-criminal-court-origins-jurisdiction-and-african-bias#sthash.wnQGWFm6.dpuf>, accessed 22 June 2019.

⁵ Articles 25 and 27 of the Rome Statute.

⁶ This might occur where proceedings are unduly delayed or are intended to shield individuals from their criminal responsibility. This is known as the principle of complementarity, under which priority is given to national systems. States retain primary responsibility for trying the perpetrators of the most serious of crimes.

⁷ Article 2 of the Rome Statute state that the Court shall be brought into relationship with the United Nations through an agreement to be approved by the Assembly of States Parties to this Statute and thereafter concluded by the President of the Court on its behalf.

⁸ Called the P5 and comprising of the United Kingdom, Russia, China, France and the United States.

⁹ Rome Statute Article 13 (b).

¹⁰ On Preliminary rulings regarding admissibility.

¹¹ On the Challenges to the jurisdiction of the Court or the admissibility of a case.

¹² Though some scholars like Cassese, and Holmes have a different view. See: Markus Benzing, 'The Complementarity Regime of the International Criminal Court: International Criminal Justice between State Sovereignty and the Fight against Impunity' *Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law*, volume 7 (2003) 591-632, R Dixon/ K AA Khan/ R May, eds, Archibold, International Criminal Courts, Practice, Procedure and Evidence (2003)1182.

court would be bound by such a decision. Referring the ICC as an independent and impartial international organisation with the power to determine its own competence is not sufficient as such.

The independence of the court and its judges only exist within the ambit of the legal framework established by the Statute and does not actually preclude the influence of other organs or question of jurisdiction and admissibility.¹³ The Statute presupposes that the court will apply the complementarity principle to Security Council referrals too. Article 53(1)(b) requires the prosecutor to have regard to the admissibility of the case when deciding whether to initiate an investigation also if the case has been referred to the court by the Security Council.¹⁴ While some argue that the court would not be bound by a determination of admissibility by the Security Council since article 24, 25, 103 of the Charter of the UN only addresses UN Member States not international organisations; others rightly contend that decisions of the Security Council under Chapter VII of the UN Charter are binding on international organisations. This is so at least in as much as they are established by UN Members States since States cannot vest an international organisation with more powers than they themselves have.¹⁵ States must not circumvent their own duties under the UN Charter by creating an international organisation which exercises its duties in contradiction to the United Nations and its organs. Since the ICC has been created by States as a complementary institution and retained the right to investigate and prosecute international crimes unless deemed unwilling or unable by the court, the Security Council may not ignore that restriction on the court's scope of action.¹⁶ Accordingly, the persuasive weight of the Security Council has the potency of making it difficult for the court to disagree with a determination by the council.

However, the question is, on who lies the burden of proving the unwillingness or inability of a state to genuinely investigate or prosecute a crime. The burden is very likely to rest on the prosecutor just as the burden of proving the guilt of an accused rests on the prosecution but unfortunately in this case, it is on the State. By the principle of complementarity there could be said to be a consensual division of labour between the state and the court yet the state may possibly waive its right to investigate and claim complementarity as a bar to admissibility.¹⁷ One of the possible grounds for such a waiver could spring up where the case is of international importance and/or politically too sensitive for the State to handle it itself. If the complementary principle is read as a safeguard of national sovereignty in the form of the right to prosecute, then it is indeed convincing to argue that a State by declining to exercise the right, under general international law, may waive its primacy and so enable the court to act. If on the other hand the complementarity principle did not exclusively protect State sovereignty, but also created a right for the individual then, such a waiver by a State would not be possible.¹⁸ This is because the State cannot unilaterally take away a right of a person that it has agreed to in a multilateral instrument.¹⁹ However, since there is no such right for the individual in the Rome statute, therefore handing over the prosecution to the international plane would not amount to a breach of an international obligation. The State concerned would fulfill its obligation by ensuring that the court investigates and adjudicates the crimes, provided the court actually initiates proceedings. Without honest co-operation from the State and the

¹³ LJ Laplante, 'The Domestication of International Criminal Law: A Proposal for Expanding the International Criminal Court's Sphere of Influence, 43 J. Marshall L Rev ,635 (2010)' *John Marshal Law Review*, vol 43 (2010) 640.

¹⁴ P Gargiulo, 'The Controversial Relationship Between the International Criminal Court and the Security Council,' in M Benzing, *supra* (n 6) 36.

¹⁵ E de Wet, 'Judicial Review as an Emerging General Principle of Law and its Implication for the International Court of Justice' 47 NILR (2000) 181.

¹⁶ J Laplante, *supra*, (n 7) 36.

¹⁷ Markus Benzing, 'The Complementarity Regime of the International Criminal Court: International Criminal Justice between State Sovereignty and the Fight against Impunity' *Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law*, volume7 (2003) 591-632, www.icc.int/otp/policy.php 4; www.mpil.de/files/pdf3/mpunyb_benzing_7.pdf, accessed December 24, 2021.

¹⁸ Rome Statute Article 19 (2)(a).

¹⁹ J Laplante, *supra*, 40.

Security Council, the success of the International Criminal Court in addressing criminal justice issues especially issues of impunity will end in a deadlock. A solution will be a resort to proactive complementarity otherwise the principle is already an excessive concession to State sovereignty. It is potentially endangering the success of the endeavour to establish the first permanent international institution with jurisdiction over the most serious international crimes.

(b) The ICC and Africa

Thus far, the ICC has undertaken at least nine investigations in Africa. While the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), the Central African Republic (CAR) and Uganda were self-referrals, Sudan and Libya were referred to the ICC by the UN Security Council, then Kenya and Mali by the Office of the Prosecutor.²⁰ The Kabila's DRC government referred the situation of ongoing violence in the Eastern DRC to the ICC in 2004, resulting in arrest warrants for six rebel leaders. This sparked off accusations that the ICC was prosecuting selectively in exchange for government cooperation. The CAR made a self-referral to the ICC in 2004 for international crimes committed on its soil. The ICC subsequently issued an arrest warrant for former DRC Prime Minister, JP Bemba, who stands accused of war crimes and crimes against humanity committed in the CAR. The Ugandan government referred the Lord's Resistance Army (LRA) to the ICC in 2005, resulting in arrest warrants for a five LRA leaders including the infamous Joseph Kony.

Kenya represented the first case in which the ICC Prosecutor invoked proprio motu principle under Article 15, allowing former Prosecutor, Moreno-Ocampo, to refer Kenya due to the 2007 election violence. The ICC concluded that the 2007/8 political election violence (PEV) amounted to crimes against humanity. The court noted that the gravity and scale of the violence, including elements of brutality such as burning victims alive, attacking places sheltering victims, beheadings and using machetes to hack people to death. The perpetrators, among other acts, allegedly terrorised communities by installing checkpoints where they would select their victims based on ethnicity, and hack them to death. They commonly committed gang rape, genital mutilation and forced circumcision, and often forced family members to watch.²¹

Kenya's President- Uhuru Kenyatta and the Deputy President -Ruto were indicted and charged for crimes against humanity and war crimes in connection with the post-election ethnic violence in 2007-08, in which about 1,200 people died.²² Uhuru Kenyatta and Ruto voluntarily submitted to the ICC for trial. Kenyan government allegedly failed to comply and refused to hand over evidence vital to the case to the ICC prosecutor. There were allegations that witnesses were bribed and intimidated. According to the prosecutors, the evidence had not improved to such an extent that Mr Kenyatta's alleged criminal responsibility can be proven beyond reasonable doubt. Consequently on 17 July 2014, ICC withdrew all charges against Kenyatta for now.²³

The Prosecutor also referred Côte d'Ivoire a non-signatory State to the Rome Statute to the ICC in 2011 following the 2010 election violence. While Côte d'Ivoire is not signatory to the ICC, it has accepted the Court's jurisdiction. Mali was referred by the Prosecutor in 2013 due to evidence of war crimes

²⁰ The International Criminal Court: Origins, Jurisdiction and the 'African Bias' South African History Online © 2015 <http://www.sahistory.org.za/article/international-criminal-court-origins-jurisdiction-and-african-bias#sthash.wnQGWFm6.dpuf>. accessed December 22, 2021.

²¹ Geoffrey Lugano, 'Assessing the Acceptance of International Criminal Justice in Kenya' <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-kenya-ruto-idUSKCN0X50Q2>, accessed November 20, 2019.

²² *The Prosecutor v Uhuru Muigai Kenyatta* ICC-01/09-02/11.

²³ ICC drops Uhuru Kenyatta charges for Kenya ethnic violence, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-30347019>, June 22, 2019.

committed by Ahmad Al Faqi Al Mahdi, leader of an Islamic extremist group Ansar Dine,²⁴ who particularly violated customary conduct during warfare by targeting religious sites.

Sudan and Libya were both referred to the ICC by the UN Security Council in 2005 and 2011 respectively. After the United Nations Security Council's referral to the ICC of human rights abuses in southern Sudan, the ICC issued two arrest warrants; one for the Sudanese Minister of State for Humanitarian Affairs accused of crimes against humanity, and the other for a Janjaweed leader. In 2009 and 2010, President Bashir also received arrest warrants. Sudan's referral stipulated that the country was to give its full compliance despite its non-signatory status. The country up until Al Bashir's dethronement in April, 2019 refused to cooperate, claiming that it would investigate its own war crimes, but not the accused men. This has been further aggravated by the African Union urging its member states not to comply with ICC investigations.

Libya received arrest warrants for Gadaffi and two of his upper-echelon leaders. Following the death of Gadaffi, Libya conflicted with the ICC over where the two remaining detainees would be tried. While under the principle of complementarity, Libyan courts were willing to try the accused, the ICC was concerned over Libyan courts' ability to do so impartially. This raised further criticisms of ICC procedure as there are no established methods or criteria for determining the competency of national courts.

South Africa stands remarkable in the history of the ICC with Africa. In the events that brought about the criticism on the so called African bias, millions of anonymous people that suffered and still suffer from these crimes as victims are often forgotten. Focus is rather given to the statements, comments and agitations of a few powerful, influential individuals. It is worth recalling that the controversy surrounding the visit of the former Sudanese president- Omar al-Bashir, to South Africa in July 2015 brought about the re-emergence of debates surrounding the role of the ICC in African States. Nonetheless, this has particularly given hindsight on South Africa's own relationship with the international prosecuting body prior to the establishment of the ICC. South Africa is the twenty-third State Party to sign and ratify the Rome Statute in 1998.²⁵ Since then, South Africa has a longstanding relationship with the ICC dating back to the country's role in the Assembly of States Parties (ASP) which pushed the Rome Statute through its ratification process. In 2002, following the establishment of the ICC, the South African government drafted the obligatory Implementation of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court Act 27 of 2002.²⁶ The Act entered into force in August of the same year. The ICC Act hailed an important moment for South Africa, as preceding domestic legislation did not include war crimes or crimes against humanity.

The Act, under section 4(3), also allows South African courts universal jurisdiction to prosecute individuals for the international crimes of genocide, war crimes and crimes against humanity.²⁷ South African courts had their jurisdiction extended to prosecuting individuals who, after committing these international crimes, are present in South Africa such as in the case of al-Bashir who had been indicted for international crime of war crimes, crimes against humanity and genocide by the ICC in 2009 and

²⁴*The Prosecutor v Ahmad Al Faqi Al Mahd* ICC-01/12-01/15-171 27-09-2016 4/49 SL T South African History Online © 2015 <http://www.sahistory.org.za/article/international-criminal-court-origins-jurisdiction-and-african-bias#sthash.wnQGWFm6.dpuf>. accessed December 22, 2019.

²⁵ South African History Online © 2015, *supra*.

²⁶ ICC Act. See: 3See Republic of South Africa Government Gazette vol 445 Cape Town 18 July 2002 No 23642 at www.saflii.org/za/legis/num_act/iotrsoicca2002699.pdf. in B A Chigara and C M Nwankwo 'To be or not to be?' The African Union and its Member States Parties' Participation as High Contracting States Parties to the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court (1998)' *Nordic Journal of Human Rights*, Vol.33, No.3, (2015) 243–268 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/18918131.2015.1105559>, accessed December 4, 2021.

²⁷ From the Archives: The International Criminal Court: Origins, Jurisdiction and the 'African Bias' South African History Online © 2015 <http://www.sahistory.org.za/article/international-criminal-court-origins-jurisdiction-and-african-bias#sthash.wnQGWFm6.dpuf>. accessed June 22, 2021.

2010. Conversely, South Africa is also granted extraterritorial jurisdiction over South African citizens and residents.²⁸ Under Article 27 of the Rome Statute, South African courts are afforded the ability to override immunities which would otherwise apply to government officials on diplomatic visits. In spite of the above provisions, South Africa ignored their international obligation to arrest Al Barshir during his visit to South Africa as expected. It is in lieu of the above facts that this research holds that the claim by South African government that they did not arrest Al Bashir because of his immunity appears weak and without legal strength. This is because South Africa cannot rely on its domestic law or even regional law to breach any provision of international law.²⁹

In *Pinochet case*³⁰ the House of Lords reversing the lower court's ruling held by a three to two decision that a former head of state is not entitled to immunity for such acts as torture, hostage-taking and crimes against humanity committed while he was in his post. The court per Lord Nicholls held that international law, in the light of which domestic law has to be interpreted,³¹ has made it plain that certain types of conduct are not acceptable on the part of anyone and that the contrary conclusion would make a mockery of international law.

(c) ICC and the United States of America Since the ICC's establishment in 2002, the Court has experienced active opposition from the US government due to the possibility that US military and political leaders will be held accountable to politically-motivated international push for accountability for their actions in warfare. These concerns were articulated particularly by the Bush administration, which threatened to veto all UN peacekeeping operations unless granted a twelve-month blanket-immunity, which was renewed for the second time a year later although not without repercussions.³² Public outcry spiked over treatment of prisoners of war in Iraq and the notorious Guantanamo Bay, an offshore prison for foreign criminals considered a threat to American national security. Resultantly, Washington was unable to renew its immunity but made a point of continuing to oppose ICC jurisdiction. Nonetheless, it must be noted that the US did respond to the human rights violations in Darfur, endorsing the UN Security Council's referral of the situation to the ICC. Under the Obama administration the US's cooperation with and support for the ICC grew substantially. The Obama administration continued to lobby for a stronger role for the Security Council in the ICC. Interestingly, when in a curious and surprising turn of events, Ntaganda of the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) on 18 March 2013, voluntarily appeared at the US embassy in Kigali Rwanda submitted himself and asked to be transferred to the Hague-based court for prosecution,³³ despite the fact that USA is not a State Party to the Statute, Ntaganda was promptly delivered to the ICC by the USA. It is remarkable that he turned himself in through an embassy of a country that is not a party to the Rome Statute. The role played by both Ntaganda and USA is impressive and quite commendable though the motivations of both are still unknown. This clearly has implications for the Court's ability to act as a neutral and independent institution.

Similar to this, in 2006 Charles Taylor Former president of Liberia who was a wanted fugitive and declared wanted for war crimes by the Special court in Sierra Leone- Sierra Leone war crimes tribunal was arrested in northern Nigeria Borno State, on the border with Cameroon and handed over to the special court for prosecution. INTERPOL issued the Red Notice for Taylor in 2003 at the request of the Special

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Article 53 of the Geneva Convention on the Law of Treaties nullifies resort to domestic/local law as a justification for breach of the strictures of international law.

³⁰ *Regina v Bartle and the Commissioner of Police for the Metropolis and Other, Ex Parte Pinochet*, on appeal, judgment of 25 November 1998, ILM (1998) 1302.

³¹ *Trendex Trading Corp v Central Bank of Nigeria* (1977) QB 529.

³² The International Criminal Court: Origins, Jurisdiction and the 'African Bias' South African History Online © 2015 <http://www.sahistory.org.za/article/international-criminal-court-origins-jurisdiction-and-african-bias#sthash.wnQGWFm6.dpuf>. accessed 22 June 2019.

³³ The BBC Report 'Bosco Ntaganda: Wanted Congolese in US Mission in Rwanda,' <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-africa-21835345> accessed 22 June 2018.

Court for Sierra Leone, which had indicted him on charges of crimes against humanity, acts of terrorism, attacks against peacekeeping personnel and other offences.³⁴ INTERPOL had a formal co-operation agreement with the Special Court for Sierra Leone which allows for the exchange of police information and the publication of Red Notices at the request of the tribunal. The arrest saved Nigeria international embarrassment of hosting a wanted fugitive.

Kenya, during the government of Mwai Kibaki was under international pressure to arrest and surrender the Rwandan fugitive Kabuga for prosecution. From the end of 1990 to July 1994, Kabuga was said to have played a role in the preparation of a plan aimed at the extermination of the Tutsis. Felicien Kabuga has been indicted for genocide, crimes against humanity as the “main financier” of extremist Hutu political groups and their armed militias which led to the massacre of an estimated 800,000 Tutsis, and other serious violations of international humanitarian law.³⁵ Kabuga was alleged to be the main financier and backer of the political and militia groups that committed the Rwandan genocide. He was co-founder and chairman of the Fonds de Défense Nationale (FDN) through which he is alleged to have provided funds to the interim Rwandan government for the purposes of executing the 1994 genocide. He is alleged to have given logistical support to the Interahamwe militia men by issuing them weapons and uniforms and by providing them transport in his company's vehicles. Kabuga fled Rwanda in 1994. As of today's date, he has resisted all attempts at arrest. To bring Kabuga to justice, the United States Government offered a reward to individuals who can furnish information leading to his arrest, transfer, or conviction. All information regarding the identity of any informant will be kept strictly confidential. The tribunal's chief prosecutor, Bubacar Jallow, says its investigators have tracked Kabuga's movements for a number of years and believe he is a regular visitor to Kenya, where the 71-year-old Hutu owns a haulage firm. Jallow flew to Nairobi to press the Kenyan government to cooperate in Kabuga's arrest. The representatives of 25 diplomatic missions to Kenya, including the EU and US, demonstrated international concern by joining Mr Jallow in a meeting with the justice minister, Martha Karua.³⁶ Kenya's assistant foreign minister, Moses Wetang'ula, denied that the government has been shielding Kabuga whereas government does not even know his whereabouts. He rather promised that the government would step up the hunt for the Rwandan fugitive.³⁷ Later tribunal investigators tracked Kabuga to Nairobi and were about to organise his arrest when they believe he was tipped off and disappeared. There is an alleged report that a former police reservist, Epaphras Waweru Muthoko, recently wrote a letter to the Kenyan president, saying he had first-hand knowledge that Kabuga was living in Kenya under the protection of senior security officials. Kabuga apparently became too much of an embarrassment to Kenya that the government declared it will seize his assets and promised to provide records of his movements to the international tribunal. The Rwanda tribunal is still seeking 9 other fugitives who are believed to be in Africa. It has arrested 27 others, most of them senior political and military figures in the Hutu regime that organised the genocide. Several, including the former prime minister Jean Kambanda have been convicted and are serving life sentences in a prison in Mali. The ICTR is primed to close down in 2015.

³⁴ 'INTERPOL applauds speedy arrest of Charles Taylor in Nigeria' <https://www.interpol.int/fr/Actualites-et-evenements/Actualites/2006/INTERPOL-applauds-speedy-arrest-of-Charles-Taylor-in-Nigeria>, accessed 20 November 2019.

³⁵ *The Prosecutor v Felicien Kabuga*, Case No. ICTR-98-44B-R7 I bis

³⁶ Press Release from International Residual Mechanism for Criminal Tribunals ICTR: Prosecutor and Representatives of Diplomatic Missions Meet Kenyan Officials, <https://unictr.irmct.org/en/news/ictr-prosecutor-and-representative>, accessed December 26, 2021. Representatives of the diplomatic missions who attended the meeting were from Canada, Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, the Czech Republic, Denmark, the European Commission Delegation, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, the United Kingdom, Norway, Switzerland, the United States of America and Rwanda.

³⁷ Kenya is not doing enough to catch Kabuga, says Prosecutor <https://www.nation.co.ke/news/africa/1066-501784-7e3ky5z/index.html> accessed 26 January 2022.

Regarding what will happen to the functions and activities that outlived the ICTR, the UN Security Council established the International Residual Mechanism for Criminal Tribunals (or “the Mechanism”), in Resolution 1966 (2010), to take over the remaining functions of both the ICTR and the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY). The Mechanism, which has been functioning since 1 July 2012, has already taken over some of the ongoing functions of the ICTR, including the enforcement of sentences of those convicted and sentenced by the Tribunal, the tracking, arrest and prosecution of fugitives earmarked for trial at the Mechanism, and the care and protection of witnesses. On 1 August 2012, the case of Kabuga was transferred to the International Residual Mechanism for Criminal Tribunals (IRM) created by the UN in December 2010 to assume some functions of the ICTR and ICTY after the end of their mandate. This includes tracking, arresting and judging the 9 fugitives still wanted by the ICTR.³⁸

3. A Critique of the ICC as a Neocolonial Venture.

Several criticisms of the ICC have underscored the tensions inherent in Africa’s unwillingness to commit to a supranational criminal justice system. African countries have undergone a significant shift from calling on all to support the ICC, to a recent call for non-cooperation and proposing amendments to the Rome Statute. This illustrates the extent to which the significant cognitive discordance has swept the continent’s previously-unanimous desire for human rights justice. Since its first case against the Congolese rebel leader Thomas Lubanga, the ICC has been criticised for its apparent bias against African leaders, as the majority of ICC cases have come from Africa. Both the AU Chairperson and Rwandan president, Paul Kagame, have accused the ICC of being partisan, neocolonial and of having an African bias, despite the fact that the first two African cases were referred by their respective governments.

The AU Assembly in July 2008, responded by passing a resolution which called on non-African states particularly EU member states to halt the practice of arresting and trying African leaders. The Assembly claimed that this “is a clear violation of the sovereignty and territorial integrity of these states.”³⁹ This has been informed by the perception that Western states were using the ICC to conduct a legal campaign against African leaders. Thus tension has continued to rise between the AU and the ICC as the AU remained convinced that EU states were abusing the ICC’s universal jurisdiction to target African leaders. This claim, has however been criticised to have no basis since the ICC has been primarily concerned with states who have accepted its jurisdiction. It may be important to note that at the sixth EU –AU Summit ⁴⁰ the two leaders of both Union⁴¹ agreed on a joint vision for a renewed partnership which is aims at solidarity, security, peace and sustainable and sustained economic development and prosperity for the citizens of the two Unions today and in the future, bringing together people, regions and organisations. It aims to promote common priorities, shared values, and international law, and preserve interests and common public goods. This includes the protection of human rights for all, gender equality and women's empowerment in all spheres of life, the rule of law, actions to preserve the climate, environment and biodiversity, but also sustainable and inclusive economic growth and the fight against inequalities⁴².

³⁸ Felicia Kabuga’s trial, <https://trialinternational.org/latest-post/felicien-kabuga> 26 January 2020.

³⁹ From the Archives: The International Criminal Court: Origins, Jurisdiction and the ‘African Bias’ South African History Online © 2015 <http://www.sahistory.org.za/article/international-criminal-court-origins-jurisdiction-and-african-bias#sthash.wnQGWFm6.dpuf>. accessed 22 June 2019.

⁴⁰ Held in Brussels on 17 and 18 February 2022.

⁴¹ Under the Co-Chairpersonship of H.E. Mr. Charles Michel, President of the European Council and H.E. Mr. Macky Sall, President of the Republic of Senegal and Chairperson of the African Union.

⁴² European Council Press release February 18, 2022 14:20.

Of the ICC's membership, Africa is the most represented region⁴³ and the majority of cases on the continent have been opened either at the request or referral of African governments, or via referral by the UN Security Council wherein African governments are represented. Indeed the Darfur referral sparked apparent tensions between the AU, the UN and the ICC. The potential reason for the AU and the Sudanese government's reluctance to allow for universal jurisdiction stems from the desire to handle the situation without outside interference and prove that the AU is, in fact, capable of resolving the continent's disputes. If that is the case, considering the principle of complementarity, the ICC would have no need to continue investigations if Sudanese national courts were undertaking their own investigations into the reported war crimes and crimes against humanity within their jurisdiction. Sudan under Al Bashir proved reluctant to allow a UN peacekeeping contingent into Darfur.⁴⁴ They conceded only when the peacekeeping mission assumed a hybrid nature co-led by the UN and AU peacekeepers which seems to be the first of its kind in UN peacekeeping history anyway.

Furthermore, the withdrawal of charges against the Kenya President and Deputy President- Kenyatta and Ruto respectively on grounds of lack of evidence gives credence to the AU's allegations. The ICC in December 2010, intervened in Kenya's 2007/8 election/political crisis after two years of domestic inaction. The court after investigation indicted and issued arrest warrants against suspects including Kenya President and Deputy President- Kenyatta and Ruto respectively who won the 2013 elections and subsequently formed the Government. There were mixed perceptions on Kenya's engagement with the ICC. Whereas President Kenyatta, his Deputy and Sang continued appearing for trials and obeying the Court's summons, the Office of The Prosecutor (OTP) consistently complained about Kenya's non-cooperation. Kenyatta's and Ruto's allies also renewed calls for Kenya's withdrawal from the ICC as they had been doing before their elections, despite their compliance with the Court's summons. According to the OTP, Kenya's non-cooperation included not turning over crucial evidence, witness intimidation and interference, as well as political and diplomatic attacks on the Court. Commenting on Kenya's cooperation, the ICC's prosecutor, Fatou Bensouda concluded that Contrary to the Government of Kenya's public pronouncements that it has fully complied with its legal obligations, it has breached its treaty obligations under the Rome Statute by failing to cooperate with investigations.⁴⁵

Kenyan authorities vehemently contested the OTP's assertions. Kenya's Attorney General Githu Muigai, claimed that they submitted evidence to the OTP and instead blamed the case termination on the ICC's incompetence. Similarly, President Kenyatta defended Kenya's cooperation, declaring that they 'cooperated because they believe in the rule of law and international justice and it was the reason for his and Ruto's voluntary submission to the Court's processes. According to President Kenyatta, 'if Kenya believed in impunity, it would not have submitted to the Courts as it did. Kenyan Deputy President William Ruto upon termination of charges against him said that the International Criminal Court case against him collapsed because he was innocent of fomenting election violence that killed 1,200 people. It could be said that having this ICC case out of the way could probably smoothen relations between the two sides of the coalition, as both the deputy president and the president are now on the same ICC-free level.

The ICC and Peace Processes

One way in which the human security impact of the ICC may be evaluated is through its interaction with the humanitarian community, particularly those organizations on ground dedicated to monitoring and assessing conflict situations. The relationship between the humanitarian aid community and the ICC is complex. While many can agree that victims of human rights violations deserve some form of justice, the timing and type of justice administered may influence the security crisis and the resources available for

⁴³ One-third of states who have signed the Rome Statute are African.

⁴⁴ <http://www.sahistory.org.za/article/international-criminal-court-origins-jurisdiction-and-african-bias#sthash.wnQGWFm6.dpuf>, accessed 22 June 2021.

⁴⁵ Geoffrey Lugano, 'Assessing the Acceptance of International Criminal Justice in Kenya' <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-kenya-ruto-idUSKCN0X50Q2>, accessed 20 November 2021.

those in need. It has been said that what would replace a dictatorship is almost as important as its removal.⁴⁶ The ICC's arrest warrant against Joseph Kony in Uganda and Omar al-Bashir in Sudan case are good examples. In a recent case, and as a reprisal for his indictment by the ICC, Omar al-Bashir of Sudan expelled humanitarian aid workers, including those from Save the Children and Oxfam.⁴⁷ According to Charles McCormack,⁴⁸ the organization was the largest provider of education, healthcare, and protection services to vulnerable populations in the Sudan.⁴⁹ McCormack claims that, because of the indictment of President Al Bashir, the Sudanese president removed NGOs based on the false assumption that such humanitarian aid organizations were cooperating with the ICC to prosecute him as a war criminal.

The argument is that the ICC's investigations and indictment of Al Bashir have undermined peace negotiations and interfered with attempts at achieving stability in the area. This argument to an extent may be valid considering Al Bashir's reaction to his indictment. Upon Knowledge of his indictment for war crimes and crimes against humanity in 2009, his government expelled about thirteen foreign aid and humanitarian groups⁵⁰ impacting severely on the thousands of internally displaced persons requiring access to healthcare, food and shelter. The Sudanese experience has led to further argument that during a temporary ceasefire agreement or post-conflict peace-building setting, the indictment of a sitting head of state may undermine already-fragile peace processes. For example, when arrest warrants were issued for Bashir and Gadaffi, both Sudan and Libya were experiencing ongoing conflict and violence, and many felt that the ICC could have caused either leader to become even more repressive and violent in retaliation. In Uganda, while the ICC had issued arrest warrants for a number of rebel leaders, this complicated the negotiation process as the rebel leaders refused to agree to a ceasefire or enter negotiations until all charges had been withdrawn.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Obviously, from the analysis above, it is crystal clear that a narrow focus on criminal justice by the ICC has the potential to destabilise peace negotiations and deepen security and safety threats. Against this backdrop, this study submits that much as indicting a sitting president for international crimes may likely increase tension and/or undermined peace negotiations and efforts to achieve stability in the area. There is need for a functional legal machinery that enables external intervention into any country where international crimes are being perpetrated in order to protect victims and human rights of the citizens in such areas without violating Chapter VII of the UN Charter. Such legal machinery must have the enabling capacity to de-robe a sitting president who perpetrates international crimes of his sovereign garb and extricate him of sovereign immunity when there is obvious engagement in acts which constitute international crimes especially crimes against humanity, or torture under customary international law. The external intervention has to be modeled to manifestly show that sovereignty has been acknowledged, respected and eventually legally violated for overriding international interest which is to check international crimes and protect human rights. This has to be done within a time frame. Consequently, it is suggested that upon international awareness that a sovereign has engaged in acts which constitute international crimes, within six months of such knowledge, the attention of the sitting sovereign concerned has to be drawn to the obvious atrocious acts through correspondence by the international community without violence. The aim is to awaken his consciousness to the obvious in case he feigns

⁴⁶Canadian International Council, "Leslie Vinjamuri on the ICC and Conflict Zones," May 6, 2012, <http://www.opencanada.org/features/leslie-vinjamuri/>, accessed 22 December 2021.

⁴⁷ Oxfam International Policy Compendium (2007) Note on the International Criminal Court. Available: <http://www.oxfam.ca/what-we-do/emergencies/oxfam-international-humanitarian-policynotes/oi_hum_policy_icc.pdf> accessed 23 December 2021.

⁴⁸ Former President of Save the Children and Oxfam

⁴⁹ With approximately 830,000 internally-displaced people served.

⁵⁰ About 6,500 aid workers.

ignorant and to redress his steps and protect his sovereign immunity. If after six months of the correspondence the situation remains the same or escalates, the regional body should be mandated by the international community to intervene, proffer solution and handle the situation within one year in order to salvage the rights of the victims and bring back stability in the region. This second step is to give regional institutions/bodies like the AU, EU etc opportunity to act and prove their desire to handle the situation without outside interference and in fact prove themselves capable of resolving their continent's disputes. Where the regional body fails to act or remains inactive within the time frame given to them, it is a clear invitation to the international community to intervene. At this stage the use of force may be inevitable. It may include forcefully removing the sitting president with an arrest warrant and appointing an interim government. Human right must be protected especially those of victims of international crimes. The international community cannot continue to protect Sovereignty in a cesspool of impunity, at the expense of human right of vulnerable civilians. The case of Sudan is a big lesson for the International community. The international effort to combat impunity for international crimes calls on sovereignty to stay pride and politics and voluntarily submit to the Rule of law. That is responsible sovereignty.